

PARALINGUISTIC MEANS AND THEIR TYPES

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Annotation: The importance of the development of paralinguistics is recognized in connection with the needs of practice and a number of sciences related to linguistics. For example, when teaching foreign languages, it turned out that learning the language itself is not enough for a complete understanding of the native speakers of the language being studied due to the presence of paralinguistic phenomena that are caused by national or cultural specifics such as the manner in which one expresses emotions, gestures, and makes human contacts.

Keywords: paralinguistic means, gestures, emotions, manner, elements of paralinguistics.

INTRODUCTION

Paralinguistics - a direction in science that arose at the turn of linguistics, psychology, ethnography, medicine and cultural anthropology in the early 50s. of 20th century in USA. Paralinguistics studies the phenomena that accompany linguistic communication of people and at the same time carry information interpreted in a certain way (timbre of voice, intonation, cough, gestures, manner of speaking, etc.). Of the various aspects of the sign theory, paralinguistics is closest to pragmatists studying the reaction of the perceiver to a sign utterance. The subject of paralinguistics is currently only being formed; therefore, it is difficult to clearly and strictly correlate it with subjects of other related sciences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are various understandings of the area under study:

- in a narrow sense, it includes sound phenomena accompanying a sound utterance;
- more broadly, all sorts of (not necessarily sound) accompaniments of oral human communication;
- finally, with the broadest approach (when the language is not associated with the definition of substance) generally covers all sorts of phenomena that accompany linguistic activity - sound, graphic, kinetic, etc.

RESULTS

In the latter case, paraklinics is also included in paralinguistics - the phenomena that accompany gesture communication. Paralinguistics also includes the features of writing, testifying to the graphic skills of the writer, his physical and mental state. Paralinguistic phenomena are a by-product of communication and, unlike linguistic statements themselves, are usually not built consciously by the speaker, but they are perceived and interpreted by the participants in the communication. Mandatory and optional paralinguistic phenomena are distinguished: the former include voice coloring, the pace of speech, the manner of writing, etc., the latter include sounds such as coughing, sobbing, smacking, as well as gestural accompaniments of speech. Being unconscious, these phenomena can be deliberately imitated (with the goal of expressing a particular state of mind or - in the case of written communication - imitate someone else's handwriting). Acting imitation of paralinguistic phenomena can be realistic or stylized (such is the doctrine of the expressiveness of gestures and facial expressions developed in the theater of the East).

In the study of paralinguistic phenomena, it is essential to find out [5]:

- how conditional they are or, conversely, natural;
- how much they are focused on the perceiver or are the speaker's completely involuntary self-expression;
- how independent they are from the actual language utterances that accompany them - i.e.
- how organized they are in the system and how much this system lends itself to existing research methods or requires new methods.

DISCUSSION

It is assumed that paralinguistic phenomena do not form independent systems and their systematic consideration is possible only in a wider context, when they act as elements of linguistic accompaniment. As for research methods, serious difficulties are palpable here, since the linguistic apparatus is insufficient for these purposes, and a special apparatus has not yet been constructed in a satisfactory form.

In the field of international communication, neglect of paralinguistic elements can lead to misunderstandings (the same gesture - for example, a nod of the head - can be interpreted by different nations as refusal or as consent). In the field of art, a misunderstanding of the paralinguistic functions of linguistic accompaniment can lead to an incorrect representation of the behavior of people of other eras or countries. An adequate interpretation of paralinguistic phenomena is essential for medicine, where the corresponding specific signs (trembling voice, nervous hand movements during speech, slow or rapid pace of speech, etc.) can serve as symptoms of certain diseases. Paralinguistic elements are also important for criminalistics (identification of the identity of the offender by the characteristic spelling of letters, by the specifics of voice, gesture accompaniment, etc.). In human communication, the

interpretation of paralinguistic elements to the perceiver consists in transcoding the information received from the speaker into signs of another code known to the perceiver (for example, the doctor recodes, “reads” the paralinguistic phenomena accompanying the patient’s speech in the form of symptoms of the disease). That is, the ability to perceive and interpret paralinguistic phenomena requires special knowledge - the more special, the more complex these paralinguistic elements. There are three types of paralinguistic tools:

- phonation - tempo, timbre, speech volume, pause placeholders (for example, uh, mm), speech melody, dialectic, social or idiolectic features of sound articulation;
- kinetic - gestures, posture, facial expressions of the speaker;
- graphic - features of handwriting, graphic additions to letters, substitutes for letters (&, §, and others) [7].

The speaker's choice of an embodiment of a paralinguistic tool is unpredictable, unlike linguistic tools; thus, the intonational design of the question in this language is set, and therefore, it should be considered a linguistic tool, while its timbre coloring is not known in advance and is a paralinguistic tool. (According to another point of view, the criterion for the allocation of paralinguistic means is not their arbitrariness, but the fact that they are not included in the phonological opposition of this language, although they are mandatory for implementation in speech).

Voice characteristics. When we give our voice a certain pitch, volume, pace and timbre, that is, change the four main voice characteristics, we complement our message, effectively complete the speech or emphasize the ambiguity of our words.

The pitch of the voice is its tone. The pitch of the voice, as a rule, changes with the volume. When people get nervous, they raise their voices, and when they try to insist on their own, then, on the contrary, they speak quietly.

The loudness of the voice indicates how the person speaks the words - loudly or quietly. Some people speak very loudly, while others, on the contrary, are quiet. In addition, the volume of the voice varies depending on the situation and topic of conversation.

Pace is the speed at which a person is talking. People often speak faster when they are happy, scared, nervous, agitated, and slower when they propose a solution to a problem or try to draw attention to a specific topic.

CONCLUSION

The ability to observe and take into account elements of non-verbal behavior of listeners allows you to adjust your speech, turn monologic speech into an active dialogue with listeners, and “draw” them into the process of mutual stimulation. Indeed, the tone of the speech largely depends on the reaction of the audience, on how much it supports or cools the speaker. Therefore, we must be able to see, feel the

"breath" of the audience in order to regulate its behavior, which is important both for the speaker speaking to the public and in a simple conversation.

However, it should be remembered that non-speech means are not independent, but an auxiliary means of communication. They prepare, accompany, comment, clarify speech, and reveal its deep essence. Therefore, before using them, you need to know about what to talk.

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